

Functional Quality for GDEMs Assessment

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Abstract— The current paradigm in geospatial data quality assessment is datacentric (internal quality) and the evaluation of the GDEMs does not escape this situation. Data quality should be evaluated as fitness for use, but this perspective is unapproachable. A new paradigm is proposed to overcome this situation by considering generic use cases that link geospatial data with its processing (algorithms). The new approach proposed by the functional quality supposes an intermediate situation between the user's and producer's perspectives (external and internal quality). This paper defines the functional quality, explains the need for this new perspective and shows an example.

I. INTRODUCTION

The concept of quality is close to everyone, it is used in colloquial language and is universally understood and intuitively accepted. In general, it can be said that a well-done work has quality. The term quality is defined in [1] as the degree to which a set of inherent characteristics of an object fulfils requirements. This definition clarifies that quality does not have to be limited to a single property of the object under consideration, but that several factors may come into play to define quality. On the other hand, what is inherent is what is proper or inseparable from things, and it is worth clarifying that here are factors that are more evident, or explicit, than others that have a more implicit character. Another interesting aspect of this definition is the one that quality refers to the fulfillment of requirements.

In this way, it is interesting to define what fitness for use is. The American Association for Quality glossary on quality [2] tells us that fitness for purpose is a «term sometimes used to define the term "quality", to indicate the degree to which a product or service meets the requirements for its intended use». Thus, we consider that term “fitness for use” implies having: i) a well-determined purpose of use and ii) the ability to evaluate the

performance level. In relation to the first component, use cases can be considered. Basically, a use case is nothing more than the description of an action or process with a certain level of formalization (e.g., using Unified Modeling Language diagrams, or any other language). Focused on a specific user requirement, the documentation of a use case must include the actors, actions, inputs, outputs and decisions necessary to achieve the proposed goal. The fitness for use approach supposes the loss of the most transcendent, abstract and general vision of quality to focus on specific use cases. For example, in the automobile sector, there are many possible users, uses and ways of driving a specific vehicle model. Considering that for a user the fuel consumption is a relevant aspect of the quality of a car model, and that it is impossible to adequately inform for all possible situations, standards, such as the New European Driving Cycle (NEDC) [3], and more recently the World Harmonized Light-duty Vehicle Test Procedure (WLTP) [4], have been adopted for dealing in this complex scenario. In the latter, a driving dynamic is adopted that tries to reproduce much better how people drive in the real world [5]. Closer to the geospatial world, there is experience in performing functional tests on web services (semantic services [6], geospatial services [7] such as WFS, WCS, etc.). And, more generally, the OASIS model [8] for web services establishes several quality dimensions on functional aspects.

For all these reasons, we consider that proposing the perspective of functional quality applied to the case of geospatial data is in line with what is already a reality in more advanced fields.

The objective of this paper is to develop a new perspective of the quality of geospatial data, in which we are guided by the example previously exposed for the automobile sector. We propose that quality be defined and evaluated in specific use cases, which means linking data and processes (algorithms). In

this way we get much better approximation to the fitness for use. We call this new perspective functional quality.

The structure of the paper is as follows: Section 2 defines functional quality in more detail. Section III shows an application example for the use case of basin delineation. Finally, Section IV presents a brief conclusion.

II. DEFINING THE FUNCTIONAL QUALITY

This paper proposes the adoption of a new level of analysis and information on the quality of geospatial data, which we call functional quality. We describe quality with the adjective functional since we propose evaluate how well the data "works/performs" in specific use cases.

Since geospatial data is used in processes, this new level of quality assessment and reporting picks up on this, linking data with algorithms, or chains of processes, to more fully consider the quality of outputs, which most directly affects to users. Thus, we define functional quality as the consistency, against a reference, of the results generated by a given algorithm (process) when applied to a given geospatial data set (e.g., a given digital elevation model —DEM— dataset that is used for the determination of a hydrographic network).

We understand the functional quality as a new perspective that can be complex and must be defined by various indices (quality measures). For example, for the case of a drainage network determined on a DEM dataset and a given algorithm, some aspects that can help to inform about the functional quality of the DEM are: displacements of the resulting network, completeness of the obtained network, topological problems present in the network, etc. That is to say, aspects that may be of interest to a user who will use that drainage network in their production processes or decision making.

Therefore, functional quality approximates the "fitness for use", but focused on a use case defined as generic and not considering particular requirements of some users or others (for example, for an engineering project, resolution requirements are different for the phases of feasibility study, preliminary design and project). With all this, a certain component of particularity is eliminated, as occurs when applying the NEDC and WLTP methods for assessing the fuel consumption in specific driving scenarios.

So, functional quality can be considered as the middle layer of a three-layer system, each of which brings us closer to quality from a different perspective: internal quality (the data-centric traditional producer's perspective), functional (use-case-centric perspective) and external quality (fitness for use perspective). In this way, a more general approach to use cases can be made without going into the problem of countless users and specific conditions of their applications, which supposes a context that is too rich and broad to be addressed. Basically, we are following

the same scheme that has been mentioned previously for the case of the automobile sector with respect to the information on vehicle consumption.

III. EXAMPLE

The first step in addressing functional quality is to define the use case to be considered. We call "base use case" the use case without being linked to a specific algorithm or process, and "specified use case" the base use case when it is linked to an algorithm or processing. In this example we consider a "basin delineation" as the base use case, which is a use case of some relevance [9]. The definition of the use case should be as detailed as possible. In our case, the proposal made by [10] will be followed. Table 1 presents the use case definition schema for this example. Key aspects are: i) the explanation of the intended use of the data, this explanation must convey an interpretative context of high value for the base use case, ii) the requirements that are established on the data from a functional perspective, they are called key performance indicators (KPI), in this example we consider three KPI based on five measures, iii) the algorithm that is considered, in such a way that the evaluation is linked to that algorithm (specified use case). We want to indicate that the KPIs are the basis of the "functional" evaluation. Therefore, KPIs must be carefully proposed by users or user communities. The international standard ISO 19157 [11] proposes several data quality measures that can be considered (e.g. six measures for the absolute or external accuracy that can be applied to 1D, 2D and 3D data, and nine measures that are specific for the vertical positional uncertainties). These measures are well defined since the ISO 19157 standard establishes a schema with twelve elements that characterize them (name, definition, description, basic measurement, etc., see annex D "List of standardized data quality measures" of ISO 19157 for details), however they present an excessively data-centric perspective typical of official geospatial data producers.

In addition to the KPIs, you also need a model that allows you to integrate the KPI's individual values into a single final or global result (a single value or an accept/reject). This model may require considerable effort from user communities to agree. The international standard ISO 19157 offers some models that can serve as an example when generating a value for the global result of the assessment (e.g. 100% pass/fail, weighted pass/fail maximum/minimum value, see annex J "Aggregation of data quality results" of ISO 19157 for details). In this case, based on user surveys, a model with five requirements has been established (see Table 1). The five KPIs and the proposed model aim to ensure three aspects ("facts" in Table 1): adequate positional accuracy, adequate statistics of the areas, and adequate spatial overlapping of the areas. This model is equivalent to the "100% pass/fail" insofar as the five KPIs are required to have acceptable values simultaneously.

TABLE I. EXAMPLE OF USE CASE DEFINITION

<i>Use case element</i>	<i>Explanation</i>	
Use case name	Determination of a hydrographic basin.	
Abstract	The user wishes to generate the planimetric delineation of a basin or set of (sub-)basins from a DEM data set.	
Algorithm	Multiple flow direction.	
Use	The result of the processing is a polygonal enclosure(s) that is(are) used to establish areas of interest for further spatial analysis.	
Requirements	Fidelity of the results:	
	Facts:	Measures:
	2D Positional accuracy of boundaries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Buffer width (95%) (m)
	Accuracy of area estimation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limited bias in the area estimation (ha) • Maximum standard deviation (ha)
Level of area overlay	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Minimum mean value of overlay agreement (%) • Maximum standard deviation of the mean overlay agreement (%) 	

Functional quality can be used to compare data (a product vs. a reference data set), but also to compare algorithms (results of a given algorithm vs. the results of a reference algorithm) using the same data set. The latter case is the one that will be presented here.

For the example case, we will consider the comparison of the results of two algorithms for watershed delineation (D8 [12] and multiple flow direction [13]) on the same data set. The data set correspond to the SRTM v3 [14] of a small area ($\approx 13 \text{ Km}^2$) in the surroundings of Allo (Navarra, Spain) (Fig. 1). This figure shows the data considered as reference (in blue) and the “product” (in red). The mean watershed size is 0.64 km^2 .

In this example the data will be considered to have adequate functional quality if:

- 1°) the positional accuracy of the boundaries of the basins is less than 50 m in 95% of the cases AND
- 2°) the bias in determining the area is less than 1000 m^2 AND
- 3°) the standard deviation of the estimation of the areas is less than 2,5 hectares AND
- 4°) the degree of agreement in the overlapping of the areas is greater than 95% AND
- 5°) the standard deviation of the average degree of overlap is less than 1%.

It should be noted that the values established for the KPIs are dependent on the scale/resolution of the geospatial data but also on the set of individuals of interest itself (the watersheds in this

case). It should be noted that although the determination of the KPIs and their associated measures is complex, the determination of the values to be considered for each measure is no less complex. This is a process in which the voice of the user (model and KPIs) must be considered, but also the voice of the processes (what can be obtained from imperfect data, algorithms and models).

Going back to the example, the results for the measures considered is $\{40 \text{ m}, 990 \text{ m}, 2.29 \text{ ha}, 95.54 \%, 0.033 \%\}$ respectively, therefore, it can be considered that the result of the analyzed algorithm adequately meet the required functional quality.

Figure 1. Delineation of basins used in the example

IV. CONCLUSION

The main contribution of this work is conceptual and has focused on justifying the need to introduce a new level of quality assessment (functional quality), which is more informative for users but, at the same time, can be applied by producers. Based on what is already being done in other fields (e.g., vehicles and web services), we consider that adopting the perspective of functional quality is a natural evolution for the case of data and its processes.

This new level of evaluation is intermediate between quality, as it is currently understood and materialized by producers, and quality in the sense of “fitness for use”. Functional quality links geospatial data with its processes, so it offers a way that is much closer to users and can help producers to be more attentive to user’s needs.

There are many use cases that can be considered for GDEM data. In this paper, a fairly simple but usual use case has been presented as an example with the aim of facilitating the understanding of the new evaluation paradigm that is proposed. The most critical issues of this new framework are the need to formalize the use cases, establish the KPIs and the model to

integrate the KPI's individual values into a single final or global result (a single value or an accept/reject). We believe that all of this should be the result of consensus among users, and that standards or guides should be established for their homogeneous application.

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